

Energy transition in Poland and Spain against changes in the EU energy and climate policy

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ABSTRACT

The European Union climate policy and the subsequent energy transition are expected to cause fundamental changes in individual EU countries, their economies, and industrial sectors. Furthermore, in order to achieve them, high financial outlays are essential. The main purpose of the article is to present a comparative analysis of the pace, directions, and main factors of the energy transition in Poland and Spain against the changes in the EU energy and climate policy. In particular, the subject of the study is the changes in the fuel structure of electricity generation (energy mix) and the changes in the concentration of energy generation. The analysis concentrates on Poland and Spain against the background of the group of EU27 countries. The study adopted a long-term perspective (1990–2020). The methodology used taxonomic measures of variability of structures and measures of concentration, as well as measures of descriptive and mathematical statistics. The result of the research proves that the EU common climate and energy policy has explicitly accelerated changes in the energy mix, both in the EU27 and in the studied countries, including those traditionally based on coal. The concentration analysis demonstrated an increase in diversification resulting in a significant increase in the share of renewable and low-carbon sources. The taxonomic analysis additionally proved that there was a parallel process towards making the energy mix of the studied countries more similar to the EU27. The limitation of the research is the adopted triangulation arrangement of the studied structures (EU27, EU15, countries that accessed the EU after 2004), enforced in this pilot research, but possible to expand the field of perception in subsequent research. What serves as a proof of the originality of the study is the fulfilment of research gaps in the long-term study of the degree of changes in the concentration of the energy mix structure of EU countries, and especially the study of the degree of intensity of its similarity. The application value of the study is its use in the energy policies of countries traditionally based on coal for the indication of the taken position, the goals, and ways to achieve them based on the experience of other countries.

1. Introduction – background and implications of the EU energy policy

In recent decades, the energy transition, understood as the shift from fossil fuels to renewable and low-carbon energy sources, has become one of the key tools to slow down climate changes (deLlano-Paz et al., 2015; Baležentis et al., 2019; Suman, 2021; Vandyck et al., 2021; Rabiej et al., 2022; Zhang et al., 2023). Intensive activities in the field of energy transition are undertaken on a global, regional, national or local scale (Loewen, 2022; Trotter et al., 2022). Transformation also takes place in

the consciousness of individual citizens (Busch et al., 2021; Ahn et al., 2021; Azarpour et al., 2022).

Actions in this area are also undertaken by the European Union (EU). Its climate and energy policy has been one of the most emphasized areas of common regulations in recent years. The energy transition taking place as a result of this policy is intended to lead to a state in which all emissions will be balanced by 2050 (Kougias et al., 2021; 63. Ghisellini et al., 2023) (climate neutrality). The problem of pollutant emissions needed to be regulated not only within the framework of the environment protection policy in the Union, but also within the common energy

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policy. Therefore, apart from one of the first directives (adopted in 1996) devoted to the comprehensive solution of the pollutant emissions problem (“Integrated Pollution Prevention and Control” - 96/61/EEC) (European Council, 1996), the European Commission adopted the first EU regulations on energy from renewable sources based on: “Energy for the future: Renewable sources of energy. White Paper for a Community strategy and action plan” of November 1997 (European Commission, 1997). It was a document of great political and strategic importance not only for the members of the EU, but also for the countries applying for EU membership, including Poland (Wiśniewski, 1998). Based on the provisions of this document, the EU countries actually started the energy transition, setting themselves the target of 12% share of renewable energy in the gross internal consumption by 2010. Significant barriers in the implementation of the assumptions of the White Paper and the unequal degree of fulfillment of the targets by individual Member States (European Commission, 2006) became the basis for the modification of the policy. To this end, in 2001 the European Parliament and the Council adopted Directive 2001/77/EC (European Parliament, 2001b) on the promotion of electricity produced from renewable energy sources (RES) in the internal market, redefining the share of renewable energy sources and the conditions for achieving the targets by 2010 (this directive was then replaced by Directive 28/2009/EC (European Parliament, 2009a; Manowska, 2018) setting new targets for a new period). In the meantime (March 2006), the European Commission adopted a more comprehensive solution for both climate and energy policy in the form of the Green Paper (European Commission, 2006). In this integrated approach to the climate and energy policy, five priority areas were defined and three main objectives were undertaken to be achieved till 2020 (Bolesta, 2006). They were as follows.

- reducing the emissions of EU greenhouse gases by at least 20% in comparison with the 1990 levels,
- increasing the renewable energy share in all the sources of used energy to 20%,
- improving the efficient energy use by 20%.

The objectives soon found their implementation within the framework of the so-called “climate and energy package”. The package includes six legislative acts, two of which were presented by the European Commission as early as in 2007, and the other four in January 2008 (2020 Climate & Energy Package, 2009). The acts concerned, among others.

- Promotion of energy from renewable sources.
- Joint efforts for the reduction of emissions (non-ETS).
- Detection and storage of carbon dioxide (CCS),
- Modification of the European emissions trading system (EU ETS).

What is very important, the package established national targets for the share of RES in the energy mix and for emissions of CO₂ (Borożan, 2022; Díaz et al., 2019; de Arce et al., 2016; Augutis et al., 2015). Undoubtedly, the ETS system has become one of the most important elements of the energy transition (Lucena-Giraldo et al., 2022; Kim and Junghans, 2022).

The European Emissions Trading System (ETS), introduced by directive 2003/87/EC (European Parliament, 2003), was implemented at the beginning of 2005. The system implementation was divided into three implementation stages called “trading periods”: 2005–2007, 2008–2012 and 2013–2020. The central element of the system is a common trade “currency” in the form of emission allowances (EUA). One allowance gives the right to emit one tonne of CO₂. The system requires the member states to draw up national plans of allowance distribution for each trading period in which the number of emission allowances will be defined for each object in particular years. The limit of the total number of distributed allowances, also called a “cap”, creates a shortage necessary for trading to occur. The enterprises which

maintain their emissions below limits granted to them can sell the surplus of allowances for the price defined by demand and supply in a given period. The enterprises which have difficulties in maintaining emissions within the granted allowances have a few possibilities to choose from. They can take measures to reduce their emissions, they can buy additional permissions and/or CDM/JI credits on the market or they can also combine these two solutions. The system can be described by the principle “polluter pays”.

As a result of adopting the climate and energy package and, to be more specific, the directive 2009/29/EC of 23 April 2009 (European Parliament, 2009b) changing directive 2003/87/EC in order to improve and extend the Community hothouse gas emission allowances trading system, the principles of the EU ETS functioning were significantly modified. The existing system of granting emissions allowances in accordance with the National Plan of Allowance Allocation was to be replaced by an auction-based system. As a consequence of negotiating the full auction system, unbeneficial to some countries (including Poland), and in the interests of the competitiveness of the EU industry, the ETS directive (Article 10a and 10c) stipulates that some of the allowances in the years 2013–2020 were supposed to be granted free of charge. Depending on the industry sector, the transition to the auction-based system was supposed to take place gradually, according to different paths and on the basis of diverse criteria. Until 2020, the ETS was then modified several times to meet changing and more ambitious climate targets included in further packages: the “Paris Agreement” (Liobikiene and Butkus, 2017) – 2015, the “Winter Package” (Rosenow et al., 2017) - 2016, the “European Green Deal” – 2019 (European Commission. Delivering the European Green Deal, n.d.) and its development - the “Fit for 55 Package” 2020 and 2021 (COM/2021/550–2020 and 2021) (European Commission. Fit for 55 Package, n.d.). The aforementioned packages shape the current energy transition policy of the EU and, together with solutions adopted in individual countries, are the main factors of decarbonisation and of increasing the share of renewable energy. However, it should be emphasized that countries of the EU are characterised by different structures of electricity production, differing availability of fossil fuels and different states of advancement in the use of renewable energy sources (Zhang and Kong, 2022; Tutak et al., 2020; Rodrigues et al., 2020). Poland is an example of a country with significant coal resources and still a high degree of dependence in terms of electricity production on hard coal and lignite. Therefore, for Poland the ongoing energy transition is one of the biggest challenges after the economic transformation (Kaczmarek et al., 2022).

Based on the arguments mentioned above, the research problem is the follow-up of changes in Poland’s energy mix related to changes in the EU27 countries (with Spain as a reference country). The key questions posed in the research are as follows: whether an impact of the EU climate and energy policy on changes in the energy mix of Poland, Spain and EU countries was observed; what are the dynamics and directions of changes in the fuel structure of electricity generation; whether the concentration of this structure is decreasing or increasing and at what pace, whether any similarities and trends can be observed, and as a conclusion, on what mechanisms pillars (directions) should the energy transition policy in Poland be based? These questions define the main purpose of the study, which is to present a comparative analysis of the pace, directions, and main factors of the energy transition in Poland and Spain against the changes in the EU energy and climate policy. The detailed study tasks stemming from the main purpose to solve the research problem were subordinated to the formulated sub-goals.

- Measure changes in the structure of electricity generation in Poland, Spain and the EU27 countries in the context of the implemented energy policies,
- Measure changes in the degree of concentration of structures in the context of the implemented energy policies,
- Compare the structures of the studied countries and their changes,

- Identify periods or points in time with increased dynamics of changes,
- Assess the impact of the climate and energy policy on changes in the energy mix of Poland and Spain compared to the EU27 countries
- Identify and measure the correlation between the structural changes in Poland, Spain and the EU27 countries.

The basic structure of the research is as follows: Section 2 reviews available literature; Section 3 covers materials and methods. Section 4 details findings and Section 5 discussion. Section 6 presents the final conclusions and limitations of the research carried out.

2. Literature review against energy transition in Poland and Spain

The Polish energy sector is primarily based on the combustion of hard coal and lignite (Wierzbowski et al., 2017; Sobczyk et al., 2020). According to Eurostat databases (Eurostat Data Browser, n.d.) (all data concerning the structure of electricity generation come from Eurostat databases), in 1990 96% of electricity and derived heat in Poland was produced using coal (56% from hard coal and 40% from lignite). In 2020 this fuel source still accounted for 68% of the country's electricity supply (44% from hard coal and 24% from lignite), which represents a decrease of 28 points. The position enjoyed by coal as the strategic anchor of Poland's energy security has undoubtedly been unshakeable for decades (Szymła, 2013). This was very much confirmed by the findings of successive documents setting out Poland's energy policy (PEP) over the next decades (ZPEP 1990-2010, 1990; ZPEP 2010, 1995; PEP 2020, 2000; PEP 2025, 2005). These policies (adopted in 1990, 1995, 2000, 2005, respectively) predicted that demand for hard coal and lignite for the energy sector would remain at a similar level or even increase. Only the energy policy adopted in 2009 (PEP 2030, 2009) anticipated a significant and steady decline in the use of hard coal and lignite in electricity production. According to forecasts, the consumption of hard coal in 2020 was supposed to be nearly 30% lower than the 2006 base, and lignite consumption would decline by 26% (Kaczmarek et al., 2022).

Even though coal continues to account for a high share of Poland's energy mix, for the most part it is the process of adapting to EU requirements that had, and still has, a decisive influence on the country's energy policy, and thus on a gradual reduction in the share of coal (Czech, 2016). The foundations of the energy sector reform and the energy transition in Poland in general are, primarily, the following.

- The process of adapting Polish law to the legislation of the European Union as part of pre-accession negotiations (since 1998) (Wensierski, 2003),
- The assumptions of the accession treaty obliging Poland to adopt several energy and climate directives in force in the Union (including, among others, the obligation to reduce emissions (European Parliament, 2001a) and increase the share of RES in its energy mix to 7.5% by 2010 (European Parliament, 2001b),
- The "20-20-20 Energy and Climate Package" and further packages (mentioned in section 1.1.),
- The introduction of the ETS System.

These acts and packages were the foundation for national regulations aiming to fulfil the RES and emission targets. These regulations and legal tools can be divided into two groups: obligations and incentives. Generally, electricity producers and sellers were limited by obligations, and renewable energy producers and prosumers were offered incentives. The most important obligations were these related to the need to prove the appropriate share of renewable energy in the energy sold or to pay a fee. Energy sellers could achieve an appropriate share of renewable energy by purchasing the so-called energy certificates of origin (the color of the certificate was indicating the origin) or by paying a substitution fee equal to the market value of such a certificate. On the other

hand, the introduction of the ETS obligated producers of energy derived from the combustion of fossil fuels to purchase emission allowances (EUA). Due to the fact that Poland was covered by derogations (European Commission, 2012), the Polish power sector was not obliged to buy all the emission allowances from the beginning. Energy companies had to increase the share of emission allowances purchased on the free market every year (in the period 2013–2020) until 2020, when all emission allowances had to be purchased.

On the other hand, the market of energy production from renewable sources was initially developing on the basis of the system of certificates of origin whose initially high price encouraged investments in RES. Later, due to, among others, the growing prices of EU emission allowances (in the years 2013–2020 the average EUA price increased from 5.2 euro to 31 euro (Raport z rynku CO₂, 2020), the energy produced from RES became more and more competitively priced. This permitted a gradual reduction in state support. It is also worth mentioning that the dynamically growing segment of prosumers was encouraged to invest through tools such as tax credits, direct subsidies, or attractive settlement systems with the grid energy supplier (Bukowski, 2012; Komoszyński, 2016; Pietrzak et al., 2021)

Despite the persistent and dominant share of coal in energy production, the above-mentioned activities gradually increased the share of other, non-carbon sources (Kaczmarek, 2022). According to Eurostat data, in the years 1990–2020 the consumption of coal in the power industry decreased by 9% with a simultaneous increase in electricity generation of 16%. This means that the changes in the energy mix were achieved by covering the increase in electricity generation through the greater use of non-coal energy sources (8.5 times). This was primarily the case with less emissive natural gas (a 16-fold increase) and renewable energy (a 15-fold increase). The use of gas was characterised by large fluctuations connected with the dates when large and medium-sized power plants and combined heat and power plants were commissioned. Gas consumption increased at its fastest rate in the years 1998–2005 (average annual growth of 49%) and in 2015–2020 (average annual growth of 22%). RES developed much later (apart from the existing large, commercial hydropower plants) with wind playing the most important role. The beginnings of the wind energy sector date back to 1997, but it only began to develop on a larger scale from 2001 onwards (average annual growth of 50%). The most rapidly developing renewable source is photovoltaics, the origins of which in Poland date back to 2011 (average annual growth of 182%), and the annual maximum occurred in 2015 (722%) (Kaczmarek et al., 2022).

Although the significant acceleration of the transformation of the energy mix gives reasons to be satisfied, it nevertheless is a source of questions about the optimal pace, directions and methods of Poland's transition to a low-carbon economy. Poland as a country at the beginning of its path to decarbonisation should use the experience of other countries that are much more advanced in the field of energy transition. Spain is a country that can be considered as an example of effective transformation for Poland.

Spain has made profound changes in its energy mix in a relatively short time. It has long been used as an example of a successful energy transition (Chapman and Itaoka, 2018). In addition, it can be considered to be a suitable benchmark for Poland due to its similar number of inhabitants (38.9 million vs. 38.1 million in Poland) and a similar volume of electricity production (152 TWh vs. 136 TWh in Poland) at the beginning of the research period (1990).

In 1990 in Spain 39% of electricity was generated using coal (28.1% from hard coal and 11.3% from lignite). Compared with Poland, the main difference was that Spain had a developed nuclear power sector which allowed to produce 35.7% of electricity. Hydroenergy was responsible for 17.2%, oil and petroleum products for 5.7% and natural gas for only 1% of electricity generation. In 2020 45% of electricity was generated from RES (bioenergy and biofuels), in which wind represented 21%, hydroenergy 13% and solar energy 8%. Hard coal (2.1%) was almost completely replaced by less emitting natural gas (26.5%). It

should also be noted that although the production of nuclear energy increased slightly (7.4%), its share in the energy mix decreased to 22% in the analysed period. These major changes in the energy mix are not a coincidence but the result of an effectively implemented energy policy aimed at energy transition towards low-carbon sources and RES (Herath and Tyner, 2019; Gómez-Calvet and Martínez-Duart, 2019; FPG24.pl, 2022; Langarita et al., 2021).

The Plan for the Promotion of Renewable Energies in Spain, approved by Agreement of the Council of Ministers at its meeting of 30 December 1999, established that energy objectives would reach a minimum of 12% contribution of these energies to Spain's energy demand by 2010 (Dirección General de Política Energética y Minas Subdirección General de Planificación Energética, 2001). In 2006 the plan and its implementation and investments already achieved the level of 14.8% of the energy generated coming from RES. This situation was reinforced by the subsequent Spanish Energy Saving and Efficiency Strategy, approved in November 2003, aimed at reducing energy consumption, contributing to improving the competitiveness of Spanish industry and reducing pollution (Rodríguez Monroy, 2002; Alcántara and Padilla, 2003). Also, in August 2005 the Spanish government approved the Renewable Energy Plan 2005–2010 (PER), which was followed by a new PER with a time scope 2011–2020 and aimed at achieving international commitments (EU and the Kyoto Protocol). The objective was to limit the growth of emissions to 37% of those of the base year, covering the difference between this figure and the Spanish commitment of 15% by resorting to flexibility mechanisms (20%) and sinks (2%) (Climent and Pardo, 2007).

Regarding the 2012–2020 stage, it was marked by the approval of Law 2/2011 of 4 March, on Sustainable Economy in March 2011 (Ley 2/2011, 2011). In it, the government marked renewable energies as a basic pillar of the energy and environmental strategy. The commitment to these energy sources is based on their reduced environmental impact compared to other energies, and on their nature as an autochthonous resource, which therefore favors energy self-sufficiency and less dependence on the outside (Costa, 2016). In short, this policy constitutes one of the bases of sustainable development, which represents one of the priorities of the Spanish policy in the long term (Chiappinelli & May 2022). Taking into account only the projected evolution (2010–2020) in the energy mix, the new law assumed a reduction in the share of electricity production from oil (from 5.5% to 2.2%), coal (8.5%–8.2%) and nuclear heat (20.6%–14.5%) and an increase in the case of natural gas (32%–34.7%) and RES (33.3%–40.3%).

In implementing the new law, the Spanish government was focused on eliminating the dependence on fossil fuels, since they must be imported (especially on oil, the share of which was reduced by half). It was also proposed to close some nuclear power plants, thus reducing their share in the energy mix by almost 6 points. However, an increase in investments and a wider promotion of RES (an increase of 7 points) were to be the source of the biggest changes.

Actions taken by the Spanish government and society resulted from the necessity to fulfill EU obligations, but also to a large extent from the responsibility for their own energy security. The pace of changes was determined by the tools and programs gradually introduced by the government in recent decades.

The presented foundations of the EU climate and energy policy, the state and changes of the energy mix in Poland and Spain and the actions taken by them towards the energy transition constitute the basis for further considerations. The question of great importance is the extent to which the EU policy and solutions applied by individual countries affect the directions and pace of changes in the energy mix.

The energy transition process and adaptation of economies and industry sectors to changing climate goals are the main focus of many scientific and expert studies of a cross-cutting nature. They concern the analysis of changes in all EU countries or groups thereof (Europe's Energy Transition, 2021; Nies, 2019; Tagliapietra et al., 2019; Papiez et al., 2021; Jonek-Kowalska, 2022), or locally concern only individual

countries, including, for example, Germany (Ohlhorst, 2015), Spain (Peña-Ramos et al., 2021), Denmark (Foxon, 2008). Also Poland was and still is an object of similar research. So far, detailed studies have focused on the determinants of the energy transition and its pace (Gawlik and Mokrzycki, 2019), its costs (Grubišić et al., 2022, Dohn and Knop, 2021; Bijańska et al., 2022) or the impact on individual industry sectors (Lew et al., 2021; Kaczmarek et al., 2022, Kramarz et al., 2021; Kolegowicz and Szymła, 2022). Many studies attempt to identify the main determinants of the energy transition process (Jonek-Kowalska, 2022). Among them, in particular.

1. Climate policy and climate change mitigation (Georgatzi et al., 2020; Calvo-Gallardo et al., 2021),
2. National resource and energy policy (Polzin et al., 2015; Stokes and Warsaw, 2017; Zhan and Wang, 2022; Adedoyin et al., 2020a; Alolo et al., 2020),
3. Technological and infrastructural changes (Henriques and Borowiecki, 2017),
4. Economic and social conditions (energy intensity, population size, social patterns of energy consumption) (Churchill et al., 2020; Kang et al., 2019; Woźniak and Pactwa, 2019; Baležentis, 2020),
5. Ecological awareness of the society (Adedoyin et al., 2020b; Náñez Alonso, 2023),
6. Geopolitical situation and availability of energy raw materials or renewable resources (Angelis-Dimakis et al., 2011; Dogan et al., 2023).

The presented sequence does not illustrate the importance of these factors on a global scale but is only a summary of them. The strength of the above factors will vary depending on the country and its specific conditions (Przychodzen and Przychodzen, 2020). Nevertheless, the very observation, additionally supported by the analysis in previous research (Keles and Yilmaz, 2020; Bamisile et al., 2022; Kamiński, 2019), allows to draw the general conclusion that only the decisive stance of governments, supported by radical and legally sanctioned actions are an effective tool for energy transition (Meya and Neetzow, 2021; Jonek-Kowalska, 2022). Therefore, considering the changes in the EU, it can be concluded that a number of elements of the EU policy, such as the introduction of the ETS system and its subsequent modifications, the introduction of EU and then national plans for reducing emissions and the share of RES, gave an economic and legal signal to the energy transition in individual countries, which should be visible in the statistics.

The literature review carried out by the authors shows that although there are a number of studies showing energy transition process, its factors and their significance in national, European or global terms, no attempt has been made to date to undertake a comprehensive, long-term study of the degree of changes in the concentration of the electricity generation structure and, what is very important, no attempt has been made to answer the question whether the energy mixes of individual EU countries are becoming more similar to each other or not. In addition to the general layer, such research may be of an applicable nature, especially for countries that are characterised by a long delay in the energy transition process and are trying to work out an optimal path of their development. Comparative research may be useful for countries still relying on coal-based energy production, such as Poland. The research findings can show them where they are now, goals to be achieved and, based on the experiences of other countries (Spain), the way to achieve them.

3. Materials and methods

The research problem, research goals and literature review are sublimated under the main hypothesis: (H) the common energy policy of the EU results in accelerated changes in the energy mix. The main hypothesis was supported by three partial hypotheses resulting from the partial

goals and the “atomization” of the research problem.

H1. Poland’s accession to the EU accelerated the process of increasing the degree of similarity of electricity generation structures in Poland to those in the European Union.

H2. The introduced EU regulations, including the climate and energy packages, stimulated and directed changes in the energy mix in Poland and Spain.

H3. The implementation of the common EU climate policy influences the degree of deconcentration of electricity generation structures in the studied countries.

The methodology and results of the research as well as the discussion of its findings provide the structure of the article. In the first step, a review of the literature related to the processes of energy transition, and its legal background in the EU, Poland and Spain is carried out. After that the research goals, hypothesis and methods forming the research framework are presented. The research results themselves have been arranged in order, beginning with the analysis of changes in the fuel structure of electricity generation (energy mix), continuing with the analysis of direction and degree of concentration of the energy mixes, intensity of structure changes of the fuel structure of electricity generation (energy mix) and finishing with the analysis of similarity of these structures in the analysed countries. In the next step the results are discussed in depth, which provides a further confirmation of the research hypotheses. The final conclusions are presented in the summary.

The research covers all the current EU countries, treating Poland and Spain separately. These are long-term studies and cover the period 1990–2020, which provides a solid basis for formulating general conclusions and assessments. The adopted scope and period of research also allows to identify real and, consequently, long-term trends in changes in structures and the possibility of determining directions of future changes in the context of the ongoing energy transition.

The research framework included two initial research planes, supported by appropriate methodological pillars. The first was a multidimensional analysis of changes in the structures of the energy mixes of Poland and Spain in the context of changes in the EU27 mix. The second level of research involved the assessment of changes in the concentration degree of structures and the assessment of the directions of their changes in the context of compliance with the objectives of the EU energy transition.

Numerous research and analytical methods were used to achieve the goals, hypotheses, and research frameworks. The structure taxonomy and concentration measures were used to analyse changes in the structures of energy mixes and to assess their similarity. Using selected measures, a detailed analysis of changes in structures, similarity, and direction of changes along with periodization of periods with increased intensity of changes or its slowing down was performed. This assessment also enabled a comparative analysis of the level of deconcentration (entropy) of energy mixes in the context of the level of diversification of energy sources (see chapter Materials and methods).

The research presented in the article was based on data from official statistics of the EU, obtained from Eurostat databases that are open and accessible free of charge. The research launched back in 1990 (beginning of the economic transformation in Poland and a benchmark year for the Kyoto Protocol) and ended in 2020 was a long-term project covering a period of 31 years. The research presents the structure of fuel sources for electricity generation (energy mix) based only on these sources which were used by EU countries. For the purposes of the research, the following groups were created: hard coal (anthracite, coking coal, coke oven coke, coal tar, other bituminous coal), lignite (lignite, sub-bituminous coal, brown coal briquettes, peat, and peat products), and solar (solar thermal, solar photovoltaic). Apart from them, the authors of the article use the term renewable energy sources (RES), which include hydro, wind, solar thermal, solar photovoltaic, tide, wave, ocean,

primary solid biofuels, other liquid biofuels, biogases, industrial waste (non-renewable), renewable municipal waste.

Structural changes were assessed with the use of the structures of energy mixes, which made it possible to assess the intensity of transformations resulting from the adjustment processes in the EU and the common environmental policy as interdependent elements, and by comparing the similarity of structures. The intensity of change (NPS), also referred to as the degree of structural dissimilarity, was measured by means of the taxonomic approach. This made it possible to determine the absolute and relative differences between the shares of individual structural components and the total impact of these changes in the same or many different structural elements at comparable moments in time (Chomałowski, 2009; Kukula, 1975). Using the taxonomy of structures, it is possible to determine, more unambiguously and comprehensively than by means of the traditional over time comparison of individual structural indicators, the degree of transformation of the structures under study and to carry out a periodization of their development regarding the criterion of the degree of intensity (dynamics) of structural changes (Archibugi and Pianta, 1996). Thus, taxonomy makes it possible to determine the directions of structural changes (Castellacci, 2008), its dynamics (intensity) and determinants (also as anticipation). In addition, it allows one to evaluate the similarity of structures between each other and over time.

$$NPS = 1 - \sum_{i=1}^n \min(p_{i0}, p_{i1})$$

where.

NPS - intensity of structural change (dissimilarity),
 min - minimum value of the components of the structure,
 p_{i0} - share of the i -th component of the structure in time t_0 ,
 p_{i1} - share of the i -th component of the structure in time t_1 .

The NPS measure assumes values in the range of (0, 1) where a value equal to zero means no structural changes, while the value 1 denotes a complete change in the structure (Chomałowski and Sokołowski, 1978). The NPS parameter makes it possible to determine the intensity of structural changes in relation to past periods, but not to determine the direction of the changes.

To analyse the interdependence of time series (as well as regression interdependencies), a critical significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$ was adopted, compared with a p-value test probability. A value lower than the critical level of significance means that one can proceed *ad hoc*, as if the null hypothesis that no correlation exists has been rejected. The degree of correlation as a numerical value is given in the text only when the condition of $p\text{-value} < \alpha$ is met. Detailed results of the regression analysis are provided in Appendix. The correlation was measured using the Pearson r coefficient (degrees of correlation: <0.1 slight; 0.1–0.3 weak; 0.3–0.5 average; 0.5–0.7 strong; 0.7–0.9 very strong; >0.9 almost full correlation).

Considering their nature and origin, we can divide them into tools of traditional descriptive statistics, measures related to the concentration curve and the Lorenz curve, special measures of concentration and measures of entropy. The best known and used in empirical research are (Nissan, 1998; Bikker and Haaf, 2002; Bailey and Boyle, 1971; Jacquemin and Berry, 1979; Acar and Sankaran, 1999):

- average value of the concentration curve for N entities (ACC),

The concentration curve is used to assess the degree of concentration of the relevant market. On its basis, it is possible to determine, among others, the discrete concentration ratio and average concentration value for N entities. The average value of the concentration curve is calculated as the arithmetic mean of the accumulated shares of entrepreneurs for the N entities with the highest shares. It is the arithmetic mean of

discrete concentration ratios calculated for the N entities with the highest market shares (Jackowicz and Kowalewski, 2002; Nissan, 1998).

$$ACC_N = \frac{u_1 + (u_1 + u_2) + (u_1 + u_2 + \dots + u_N)}{N} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N CR_N}{N}$$

It combines the information contained in individual discrete indicators (from the ratio for one to the ratio for N entities). The mean value of the concentration curve for N objects, as opposed to the discrete index for all objects equal to 100%, will provide information about the concentration of contributions. Its average value is in the range [0–100% or from 0 to 1].

- Rosenbluth coefficient (RC),

It is used to measure the concentration (or unequal distribution) of N participants, who each have a share h_i and a rank i (ordered according to decreasing shares). The Rosenbluth index is based on a graphical representation of the market shares: the market participants are entered on the X-axis (sorted according to the decreasing order of size), on the Y-axis the market shares for the first, the first two, the first three (etc.) market participants. The result is a curve of market shares from zero to 1 (100 percent) (Rosenbluth, 1955).

$$RC = \frac{1}{2A} = \frac{1}{2 \left(\sum_{i=1}^n ih_i \right) - 1}$$

where.

- h - the frequency of the respective expression; i constitutes the rank of the feature bearer;
- A - the area above the concentration curve; since it is 0.5 for a single participant (100%)
- the curve halves the square from (0 | 0) to (1 | 1) - the area is multiplied by 2; with a maximum concentration (complete inequality) the Rosenbluth index is therefore 1.

- Gini concentration coefficient (GC),

The Gini concentration index, also known as the concentration ratio, is probably the most common statistical index employed in social sciences for measuring concentration in the distribution of a positive random variable. It is mainly used in economics (Bedau, 1976).

$$GC = \frac{1}{2xn^2} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n |x_i - x_j|$$

The Gini coefficient varies between 0 (the case of perfect equality) and 1 (perfect inequality), and it is invariant under scale transformations. It is equal to 0 if all individuals have the same income value, and equal to 1 if all people but one have zero income, while one individual owns the entire amount of income.

- entropy coefficient (EC) and standardized entropy coefficient (SEC),

The information entropy theory introduced by Shannon in 1948 is a measure of the average information value of a stochastic system. Based on the definition of information entropy, information entropy of the j th indicator of the evaluation matrix Y is defined by (Wang et al., 2015):

$$EC = -k \sum_{i=1}^n y_{ij} \ln y_{ij}$$

where, $E_j \geq 0$; $k \geq 0$. Constant K is only affected by the number of system samples m . For a system with total disordered information, the amount of order is zero with maximum entropy, $E = 1$. Consequently, $0 \leq E \leq 1$. The following equation can be derived:

$$k = \frac{1}{\ln m}$$

- Herfindahl-Hirschman concentration factor (HHI),

The degree of structural concentration is also measured by Herfindahl-Hirschman Index (HHI) which is calculated as the sum of the squared shares of all the components of the structure:

$$HHI = \sum_{i=1}^N x^2$$

where.

- x - component share,
- N - number of components.

The HHI index lies within the range of (0, 1). The higher the HHI value, the greater the concentration. It is calculated in such a way that the value of the components has a greater impact on the value of the HHI than their number (Bongard et al., 2007).

It is extremely difficult to indicate which of the measures is the best in examining the structures because each of them has specific advantages and disadvantages. To illustrate the differences between the measures, an empirical study was carried out on a fixed data set using the largest set of measures, and then the obtained results were analysed.

The article is a part of a series of publications on the energy transition conditions and determinants.

4. Findings

The conducted research, in addition to direct comparisons of Poland and Spain, requires a comparison with the values characteristic for the entire EU, which is particularly important in relation to the common climate and energy policy. The strong population growth in Spain observed since 1999 and the lack of changes in Poland resulted in a significant diversification of the analysed countries (Fig. 1). An outlined population growth trend is observed in the EU27 without clear periods of its pace change. The comparison of the electricity production volume (Fig. 2) also shows similar values in Poland and Spain in 1990. Then, as in the case of the population, a high increase in production in Spain with a small increase in Poland resulted in a clear differentiation in the volume of electricity production in these countries. In the production of electricity in Spain and in the EU27, a turning point is clearly marked in 2008, which coincides with the implementation of the EU climate and energy package (3 × 20% package). An annual decrease in electricity production was observed since 2008 both in the EU27 and in Spain, while in Poland there was a further increase. A similar tendency was observed in energy production per capita (Fig. 3) despite the strong increase in the population in Spain and the opposite tendency observed in Poland. The change in electricity production in Spain is characterised by a similar course as in the EU27, but it is completely different than in Poland. Changes in the trends in Poland and Spain encourage a detailed analysis of the changes taking place in the structure of the energy mix and its evaluation in the context of introducing further national and EU tools of the energy and climate policies.

4.1. Changes in the structure of electricity generation

The high level of differentiation in the production structure in the EU27 countries (Fig. 4) along with the decreasing share of fossil fuels and nuclear energy shows a sustainable change, which was also observed on the basis of descriptive statistics (Fig. 5).

The last two observations (2010 and 2020) show an increase in the share of fuels such as hydro, wind and solar with a simultaneously

Fig. 1. Population (in millions) of Poland and Spain compared to the EU27 (1990–2020).
 Source: own study based on Eurostat, available online: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/data/database> (accessed on 22 May 2022).

Fig. 2. Electricity production in Poland and Spain compared to all EU countries electricity production (in TWh) – 1990–2020.
 Source: own study based on Eurostat, available online: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/data/database> (accessed on 22 May 2022).

decreasing share of fossil fuels and nuclear heat, indicating the progressive process of change with targeted goals. In the EU27 countries, compared to 1990, there was a 17.52% decrease in the share of fossil fuels, with the exception of natural gas, the share of which increased by

11.89% to the level of 20.13% in 2020 and a decrease of 7.47% in nuclear heat compared to 1990. The targeted EU energy policy is also confirmed by a significant increase of 24.99% in the share of RES. Descriptive statistics show a sustained trend without clear sharp changes, pointing to a sustainable energy policy pursued. In 1990 the production structures of Spain and EU27 were similar, but in the following decades the structure of Spain (Fig. 6) clearly differed, which was observed in a decrease in the share of fossil fuels of 13.37%, with a simultaneous increase in natural gas of 25.51%. The share of RES in energy production increased by 26.94%, which was mainly due to the increase in electricity obtained from wind (+21.43%). The analysis of descriptive statistics (Fig. 7) shows significant changes in the structure of energy production in Spain, especially when compared with the EU27. The structure of production in Poland (Figs. 8 and 9) in 1990 was characterised by the dominant share (97.52%) of fossil fuels with the observed change but with a low level of change intensity (−15.91% compared to 1990), and with a significant increase in the share of natural gas (+10.01%). A clear change in the Polish mix was noticed only in 2010, and then in 2020 its intensification which was caused by the increase in the share of wind, hydro and solar.

4.2. Directions and degree of concentration of the energy mix

The assessment of the level of changes in the concentration of the

Fig. 3. Share of Poland and Spain in the EU27 electricity production in 1990–2020 and per capita.
 Source: own study based on Eurostat, available online: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/data/database> (accessed on 22 May 2022).

Fig. 4. The structure of electricity generation in EU27 in 1990, 2000, 2010 and 2020.

Notes: □ – standard deviation; mean determined by the center of the figure ↓↑ – minimum and maximum values.

Source: own study based on Eurostat, available online: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/data/database> (accessed on 22 May 2022).

Fig. 5. Descriptive statistics of the variability of the structure of electricity generation in EU27 in 1990–2020.

Source: own study based on Eurostat, available online: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/data/database> (accessed on 22 May 2022).

structure of the energy mix in the EU27 countries (Fig. 10) indicates its clear process of deconcentration, especially since 2007 (ACC and Gini coefficient). The results outlined above provide an unequivocal basis for the confirmation of the main hypothesis (H). Similar results were obtained with the use of the Rosenbluth coefficient, while the value of the HHI measure began to decrease since 1997, indicating a progressive

process of deconcentration. The entropy measures indicate a progressive structure scattering process since 1997. The assessment of changes in indicators clearly allows to distinguish two years of intensifying the dispersion process, that is 1997 and 2007. At the same time, in all measures, a deceleration of the tendency to deconcentrate the structure of the mix was observed since 2019.

Fig. 6. Structure of electricity generation in Spain in 1990, 2000, 2010 and 2020.

Notes: □ – standard deviation; mean determined by the center of the figure, ↓↑ – minimum and maximum values.

Source: own study based on Eurostat, available online: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/data/database> (accessed on 22 May 2022).

Fig. 7. Descriptive statistics of the variability of the structure of electricity generation in Spain in 1990–2020.

Source: own study based on Eurostat, available online: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/data/database> (accessed on 22 May 2022).

The analysis of the concentration of Spain’s energy mix (Fig. 11) is characterised by slightly higher values than EU27, which is due to the higher share of nuclear heat, hard coal, and the subsequent increase in the share of natural gas. The analysis of concentration measures with the use of the Gini, Rosenbluth and ACC coefficients allows to indicate 2008 as the starting point for a strong increase in the deconcentration of the structure of the energy mix. The above dependence is also confirmed by the entropy measures and the HHI concentration measure. In the structure of the Spanish mix, a strong increase in deconcentration began a year later than in the EU27, despite Spain’s share in the EU27 mix. As in the EU27, after 2019 the process of deconcentration slowed down and was even reversed. The results outlined above provide an unequivocal

basis for the confirmation of the partial hypothesis (H3).

In Poland’s energy mix, significantly higher values can be observed than in the EU27 and Spain (Fig. 12). The above situation is influenced by the dominant share of hard coal and lignite. Like in the EU27, the key year in the deconcentration process was 2007, when a significant intensification of the deconcentration of the structure began (HHI, SEC, EC, ACC and Gini). Until 2007 changes in the energy mix were negligible without a clearly defined trend. No slowdown of the process was observed in the Polish mix after 2019, unlike in the case of the EU27 and Spain. The changes observed after 2007 are characterised by high dynamics, which may indicate an ongoing process of adaptation to the requirements of the common climate and energy policy, including the 3

Fig. 8. Structure of electricity generation in Poland in 1990, 2000, 2010 and 2020; (b) The Descriptive statistics of the variability of the structure of electricity generation in Poland in 1990–2020.

Notes: □ – standard deviation; mean determined by the center of the figure, ↓↑ – minimum and maximum values.

Source: own study based on Eurostat, available online: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/data/database> (accessed on 22 June 2022).

Fig. 9. Descriptive statistics of the variability of the structure of electricity generation in Poland in 1990–2020.

Source: own study based on Eurostat, available online: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/data/database> (accessed on 22 June 2022).

× 20% package. The results outlined above provide an unequivocal basis for the confirmation of the partial hypothesis (H3).

4.3. Structural changes of energy mix

Changes in the structure of electricity generation in the EU27 countries indicate a balanced change of low intensity (0.021 annual average), which in 2020 resulted in a structure change of 0.374, compared to 1990 (Fig. 13). An observation of the annual rate of

changes in NPS allows to distinguish two periods of intensity increase, i. e. from 2001 to 2005 and from 2007 to 2020 (annual average 0.032). The results outlined above provide an unequivocal basis for the confirmation of the partial hypotheses (H1 and H2). Significantly more intense changes in the structure of the production mix were observed in Spain, especially until 2009 (annual average 0.056), where the structure changed by 0.525, compared to 1990. After 2009, the intensity of changes slowed down and the tendency to return to the previously existing structure was reversed until 2014, when the structure began to

Fig. 10. Measurements of concentration and dispersion of the structure of the energy mix in EU27 in 1990–2020.
 Notes: RC - Rosenbluth coefficient, GC - Gini concentration coefficient, ACC - average value of the concentration curve for N entities, SEC - standardized entropy coefficient, EC - entropy coefficient, HHI - Herfindahl-Hirschman concentration factor.
 Source: own study based on Eurostat, available online: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/data/database> (accessed on 22 June 2022).

Fig. 11. Measurements of concentration and dispersion of the structure of the energy mix in Spain in 1990–2020.
 Notes: RC - Rosenbluth coefficient, GC - Gini concentration coefficient, ACC - average value of the concentration curve for N entities, SEC - standardized entropy coefficient, EC - entropy coefficient, HHI - Herfindahl-Hirschman concentration factor.
 Source: own study based on Eurostat, available online: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/data/database> (accessed on 22 June 2022).

Fig. 12. Measurements of concentration and dispersion of the structure of the energy mix in Poland in 1990–2020.
 Notes: RC - Rosenbluth coefficient, GC - Gini concentration coefficient, ACC - average value of the concentration curve for N entities, SEC - standardized entropy coefficient, EC - entropy coefficient, HHI - Herfindahl-Hirschman concentration factor.
 Source: own study based on Eurostat, available online: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/data/database> (accessed on 22 June 2022).

Fig. 13. The dissimilarity (variability) of the structures of the energy mix in the EU27, Spain, Poland (1990–2020).
 Source: own study based on Eurostat, available online: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/data/database> (accessed on 22 June 2022).

change again. The rate of changes in the NPS of the Spanish energy mix in the y/y relationship is characterised by significantly higher values than in the case of Poland and the EU27 (Fig. 14).

The intensity of changes in the energy mix of Poland was characterised by low values, indicating slight changes in the structure. Changes introduced in the structure of electricity generation in Poland were small

in scale (NPS = 0.087, annual average 0.010) until 2007, compared to 1990. In the years 2008–2020, the intensity of changes in the generation structure was already three times as high (NPS = 0.283 in 2020, 0.029 annually on average) as in the previous years. The results outlined above provide an unequivocal basis for the confirmation of the partial hypothesis (H2).

Fig. 14. Differences in structural variability in the EU27, Spain, Poland (1990–2020).
 Source: own study based on Eurostat, available online: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/data/database> (accessed on 22 June 2022).

A comparative analysis of the differences in the NPS values of Poland and Spain in relation to the EU27 clearly indicates a high impact on the change in Spanish mix, while the changes in Polish mix slowed down (except 7 years).

The assessment of the correlation between the intensity of the change in the structure of the energy mix of the EU countries (excluding Poland and Spain) (independent variable) indicates an average coexistence of a positive relationship with the intensity of changes in the structure of the mix in Spain (dependent variable) (Pearson = 0.48) since 1990 (the entire period of Spain’s participation in the EU) – see Table 1. The p-value at the level of 0.008 indicates a statistically significant relationship, confirming the existing relationship. The assessment of the interdependence of the energy mix structure of the EU (independent variable) and Poland (dependent variable) was divided into two periods: 1990–2003 (the period before the accession) and 2004–2020 (after the accession to the EU). In the first period, an average relationship was recorded (Pearson = 0.48), but the p-value was at the level of 0.09, which means that this relationship was not statistically significant. It is completely different after Poland’s accession to the EU, where the correlation was observed in a very strong positive relationship (Pearson = 0.71) with a high matching of the variables ($R^2 = 0.50$) and the p-value equal to 0.001. The above results confirm the existence of a very strong correlation between the intensity of changes in the structure of the EU and the structure of the Polish mix after 2004, which confirms the main hypothesis (H).

A comparative assessment of the similarity of the structures of the energy mix of Poland (Ap. Matrix 1) and Spain (Ap. Matrix 2) indicates an intensive process of differentiation (dissimilarity) of the structures

until 2010 (NPS = 0.82) – Fig. 15. After 2010 there was a reversal of the trend and the commencement of the similarity process. The results outlined above provide an unequivocal basis for the confirmation of the partial hypothesis (H1). In 2020 the structures of both countries were dissimilar, as evidenced by the value of NPS = 0.70. A comparative analysis of the mix structures of Poland and Spain in relation to the EU27 countries (Ap. Matrix 3) shows a high similarity of Spain to the EU27 (NPS = 0.16 in 1990), with the process of differentiation (dissimilarities) and a reversal of the trend after 2010 (NPS = 0.18 in 2020). The structure of Poland was significantly dissimilar to the EU27 mix (NPS = 0.61 in 1990), with a slightly outlined similarity process after 2009, but with a low intensity of this process (NPS = 0.57 in 2020). When excluding Poland and Spain from the EU27 (Ap. Matrix 4) countries in the analysis of the similarity of structures, higher values of dissimilarity can be clearly observed (in 1990 NPS = 0.65 for Poland and NPS = 0.17 for Spain). We can observe a slow process of the Poland’s mix becoming similar to the EU27/EU25 mix with significant acceleration from 2009. The structure of Spain evidently changed in the direction of differentiation until 2009, when the trend was reversed with a clearly observable acceleration of the similarity process.

5. Discussion

The future and the development of the energy sector is one of the most important problems both in national and global politics, especially in the current political situation. On the one hand, the limitation of the use of fossil fuels in the energy sector results from the new legal conditions related to climate protection. On the other hand, limiting the use

Table 1
 Results of the univariate regression analysis (significant results only).

Dependent variables	Independent variables (explanatory variables)						
	Constant	Coeffi-cient	Pearson	Standard Error of Regression	R-squared	p-value	Observations
Poland 1990–2003	0.016	0.712	0.484	0.004	0.234	0.093	13
Poland 2004–2020	0.006	−0.395	0.706	0.007	0.499	0.001	17
Spain 1990–2020	0.034	1.449	0.477	0.024	0.228	0.008	30

Source: own elaboration

Fig. 15. Comparative analysis of changes in the dissimilarity of structures (NPS) of the energy mix of Poland, Spain in relation to the EU 27 and EU 25 (structure excluding Poland and Spain) in the years 1990–2020.

Source: own study based on Eurostat, available online: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/data/database> (accessed on 22 June 2022).

of the owned resources significantly reduces the energy security of countries such as Poland (Manowska, 2019). The importance of the energy transition while maintaining energy security has been the subject of many scientific studies aimed at finding the main determinants of changes and the optimal path of the transition (Augutis et al., 2015). It is particularly complicated in a situation where individual EU countries are characterised by large differences in the availability of energy sources and their use, which is well demonstrated by Jonek-Kowalska's research (Jonek-Kowalska, 2022). These studies also show that there are significant differences in the pace of changes in the energy mix, and among the EU countries it is possible to identify change leaders and laggards. Unfortunately, as confirmed by the conducted research, Poland is in the second group. Poland's delays are partly due to the later accession to the EU and the existence of many transition periods, including the derogation under the ETS, and undoubtedly due to lack of sufficient financial resources for a quick transition from energy generation dominated by coal-based energy to less or low-emission sources. However, the reason may also be the low determination of the national authorities in the absence of EU requirements. It should be emphasized, however, that changes in the energy mix have significantly accelerated in recent years (Sheykha and Madlener, 2022; Dohn and Knop, 2021). Based on the analysis carried out, it can therefore be argued that the European environment was a fundamentally important factor leading to the establishment of RES support in Poland. It prompted the country to adopt a relatively ambitious energy policy targets and to accelerate the changes in the energy mix (after 2007/2008). This phenomenon is confirmed by the results of measures of concentration of Poland's energy mix after the accession to the EU and after the introduction of the 3 × 20% climate and energy package (2007–2009). It can therefore be stated, which is also confirmed by Jankowska (2010), that without the external EU pressure there would not have been an energy and climate policy in Poland even half as ambitious as it is now (Jankowska, 2010; Ceglarz and Ancygier, 2015). EU influence explains the very fact that Poland has had RES support in the first place. In the first phase (until 1999), RES still seemed rather a distant, futuristic idea, which was associated with modernization. A particularly strong impact of this policy was observed in the EU countries after 2010, including both in the Polish and Spanish energy mix, which is confirmed by the results of the conducted research. The Europeanization process observed on the basis of the data analysis shapes the available support systems and puts pressure on the authorities of the Member States so that individual countries do not stand out from the rest of the Union. It can therefore be concluded that there was an EU influence on public consultations (especially in areas related to the environmental policy), which was a major factor in involving a wider group of stakeholders in the development and evaluation of policy proposals (Cianciara, 2015; Goyal et al., 2022; Kramarz et al., 2021; Przybylska et al., 2023). At the time of the political, social and economic transition from communism, “the West” epitomized by the EU, was perceived as a role model. Hence, the dominant diffusion mechanism was emulation (Ancygier and Szulecki, 2014) and, as a result, the pace of changes in Poland was slower than in Spain and in the EU. As Poland's EU membership moved from a distant possibility to a negotiable reality, EU conditionality and the necessity to comply with “Acquis Communautaire” became a necessity, and Europeanization, understood as harmonization of domestic policy with EU norms and expectations, accelerated. The results of the conducted research clearly show that the common energy policy unambiguously leads to a deconcentration of the energy mix, providing EU countries with a higher level of flexibility of operation.

However, the dynamic changes in the Polish energy mix were influenced not only by the regulatory pressure from the European Commission, but also by other factors, including a change in the thinking of international business that sees opportunities in the energy transition and technological development increasing the competitiveness of energy from renewable sources (Brzóška et al., 2022). Poland has significant coal resources, which undoubtedly play and will play the role

of a stabilizer of energy security in the coming years, which is of key importance in the context of the import of energy resources or energy independence. This specific security buffer, however, significantly contributes to the low pace of changes in the structure of the Polish mix - the lack of non-economic external stimuli.

Taking into consideration these circumstances, the question may be asked whether Poland will be able to adapt its further measures to the energy and climate policy of the European Union. The EU's new energy policy, shaped by the “European Green Deal” adopted in 2019 (European Commission. Delivering the European Green Deal, n.d.) (COM/2019/640-2019, European Commission, 2019) and its development - the 2020 and 2021 “Fit for 55 Package” (COM/2021/550-2020 and 2021, European Commission, 2021) (European Commission. Fit for 55 Package, n.d.) is focused on decarbonisation and the development of alternative and renewable sources of electricity to an even greater extent than before. Furthermore, the policy affects coal-fired power plants, which are the basis of the Polish energy system and, therefore, it may be perceived as a threat to Polish energy security (Brodny and Tutak, 2023; Tomaszewski, 2020; Bijańska and Wodarski, 2024). Under these circumstances, it becomes important to ask the question how Poland is adapting and will adapt its energy and climate policy in the future, on the one hand, and implement specific actions aimed at achieving the EU climate goals on the other. Therefore, what is the impact of the latest EU legislation on the Polish regulations and specific decarbonisation measures? First of all, the latest EU regulations had a decisive impact on the shape of the new Polish planning documents: National Energy and Climate Plan for the years 2021–2030 (NECP 2021-2030, 2019) and Energy Policy of Poland until 2040 (PEP 2040, 2021). According to these documents, Poland undertakes to significantly reduce and then abandon coal as a source of electricity. It is planned that by 2030 the share of coal in energy production will have fallen to 56% (32% should the prices of emission allowances be very high) and 28% (11%) by 2040. By 2049 – in accordance with the agreement signed in 2021 by the government with mining trade unions, hard coal mining in Polish mines is to end (Social Agreement, 2021). However, many experts point out that due to a number of technical factors (lack of exploitation of new coal seams), rising mining costs and the tightening of the ETS system, the coal mining may come to an end even before 2040 (Derski, 2023; Kaczmarek et al., 2022; Sawicki, 2023). According to the Territorial Just Transition Plan for the Łódź Voivodeship (TJTP, 2021; Żak-Skwierczyńska, 2022) approved by the European Commission, the exploitation of lignite deposits is to be shorter. The last mine is to be closed in 2038 when the last lignite power plant – Bełchatów – one of the largest CO₂ emitters in the European Union is shutdown (Nowakowska et al., 2021).

According to PEP2040, the process of phasing-out coal is to be accompanied by further development of RES. It is mainly about wind and solar energy. Wind energy has so far faced significant legal barriers in Poland, the detailed analysis of which is presented by Gnatowska and Moryń-Kucharczyk (Gnatowska and Moryń-Kucharczyk, 2019). However, the biggest legal barriers concerned onshore power plants. The implementation of the new energy policy is a significant support for offshore wind energy – as explained by Drożdż and Mróz-Malik (Drożdż and Mróz-Malik, 2020). Support for offshore wind energy is to be guaranteed, among others, by the signing of the Act of 17 December 2020 on the Promotion of Electricity Generation in Offshore Wind Farms (Act of 17 December, 2020). As a result of the legal changes, investments in offshore wind farms are already prepared. Plans to build a power plant have already been announced by three large international consortia (together with Polish partners) and two large energy companies from Western Europe (Wirkus, 2023). As a consequence of PEP2040, offshore wind plants should reach 11 GWe of installed power capacity in 2040. The second pillar will be solar energy, which, owing to the incentives provided so far, has been developing at a significant pace (as shown by the research carried out). Unfortunately, in this respect, significant progress has been, to some extent, hampered by changes to the prosumer settlement system, the result of which is a system that is less

favourable (Kaznowski and Sztafrowski, 2023).

Due to its seasonality and significant daily fluctuations RES require, among other things, the adaptation of the power grid to distributed energy production and the development of energy storage systems (Adamska). Above all, however, the development of the power grid requires significant financial resources. It is estimated that the investments planned in PEP2040 in new capacities in conventional energy and RES should be accompanied by expenditures on power grids of PLN 500 billion (ca €110 billion) (Elzbieciak, 2023). Currently, a large part of investments in power grids is possible owing to the European funds (Szafran, 2023), which were further increased after the introduction of the REPowerEU programme – an additional €25 billion (Skłodowska, 2023). In order to accelerate the development of energy storage, in December 2022 the Polish government launched a program aimed at co-financing the creation of home energy storage (Program, 2024). The development of RES in Poland, while moving away from the use of coal, requires the provision of an alternative, stable energy source that can smoothly regulate energy production in the event of fluctuations in production from RES (Kaznowski and Sztafrowski, 2023). The necessity to move away from coal-fired power generation resulted in the intensification of work on the development of gas and nuclear energy. Several new gas-fired power plants are currently under construction or at the stage of selecting a contractor (the largest four with a total capacity of 4850 MW) (Oksińska, 2023a). These investments were made based on the experience of other Western economies (Denmark, Germany), for which gas was to be a transitional fuel in the decarbonisation process. However, the departure from using Russian gas in response to the war in Ukraine has led to a change in the forecasts for energy production from this fuel in the future (reduction from 33% to 15% in 2040) (Smoleń, 2023). According to the assumptions, the decrease in the production forecasts does not mean the suspension of the investment process, but instead the use of gas-fired power plants during the highest demand peak and the use of turbines adapted to hydrogen co-firing or the use of hydrogen as the primary fuel in the future (Oksińska, 2023a; Klebes, 2021). Wider use of hydrogen in electricity and heating, as well as the use of natural gas infrastructure for the development of a hydrogen-based economy, is included in the Polish Hydrogen Strategy until 2030 with an outlook until 2040 (PHS 2030, 2021). The PHS is a strategic document of the Polish Government that sets out the main objectives for the hydrogen economy development in Poland and the actions needed to achieve them.

The new situation related to natural gas supplies has also become a motivation to accelerate work on a nuclear energy programme. The Polish Nuclear Power Programme (PNPP, 2020), a strategic government document, defines the tasks necessary for the construction of the first nuclear power plant in Poland. The programme assumes the completion of the construction of the first Polish nuclear power plant by 2033. In 2023, an environmental decision was issued for the selected location of the power plant (PEJ, 2023b) and the first contract for the design of the power plant in AP1000 reactor technology was signed with the American company Westinghouse (PEJ, 2023a). However, there is a number of doubts connected with the Polish nuclear programme both in terms of the possibilities and methods of financing the project (Kołacińska and Sasin, 2016; Sawicki and Horbaczewska, 2023; Sobczyk-Grygiel, 2022; Kolegowicz and Sierpińska, 2020) as well as the actual completion date (Ciepiela, 2023; Sawicki, 2024). Fearing for the success of the Polish Nuclear Power Programme, the government, through the largest of its energy companies (ORLEN), is simultaneously working on the development of small nuclear reactors (SMR - small modular reactor) in Poland in the BWRX-300 technology offered by GE Hitachi – the assumption is that there will be 6 of them (Bowen and Saha, 2023). The implementation of the SMR investment is to be less time-consuming (an SMR can be built in just 3 years from the start of construction) and less cost-intensive. The first SMR reactor is planned to be commissioned in 2029 (Oksińska, 2023b). By 2040, both gas-fired power plants and nuclear power plants are expected to protect Poland from energy deficit

caused by the assumed accelerated pace of decarbonisation and provide stable support for energy from RES.

Although the measures of the Polish government described above are often far distant in time, they are a clear sign of difficult and radical changes that are adapting the Polish energy sector to the guidelines resulting from the long-term energy and climate policy of the European Union.

Looking at the above-mentioned decisions, Poland is significantly different compared to Spain, which much earlier followed the path of decarbonisation and popularised renewable energy sources. Currently, Spain is free from the ballast of coal-fired energy and can set itself much more ambitious goals, as evidenced by those contained in both the National Energy and Climate Plan 2021–2030 (NECP) for Spain (Ministry for Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge, 2021) and the strategic document Spain 2050 (National Office of Foresight and Strategy of the Government of Spain, 2021).

From the foregoing considerations, it can be concluded in general that the large diversity of the EU27 countries in terms of their energy resources does not allow to develop a one-direction energy policy. This policy must therefore contribute to building a high level of diversification with key climate goals set, on the basis of which individual countries will shape their internal energy policies in the context of their energy resources (Zawadzki et al., 2022). The underdevelopment of Poland in the area of energy transition, as shown in the research and discussed above, may turn out to be an advantage in a sense, because when building its transition policy, Poland may take advantage of the positive and negative experiences of other countries. The experiences in the energy transition of countries which, like Poland, were largely dependent on coal (e.g. Germany, UK) have been widely described (Ohlhorst, 2015; Kaliski et al., 2011). An interesting analysis of national transition paths was also carried out by Chapman and Itaoka (Chapman and Itaoka, 2018) in order to find the optimal path for the transition in Japan. The analysis of these and other studies may be the basis for the construction and critical assessment of one's own actions also in the face of the challenge of "coal-to-green transition".

The current analysis allows to formulate the main pillars (directions) of Poland's energy policy in order to meet EU obligations and accelerate the processes of energy transition.

- Removal of regulatory barriers to the development of wind and solar energy,
- Government investments in the expansion and modernization of the power grid infrastructure, which constitutes a bottleneck for the development of RES,
- Acceleration of design works and investment contracts for the construction of a nuclear power plant, which is a stable source of covering energy demand in the face of a significant amplitude of fluctuations related to RES,
- Modernization of coal-fired units in large power plants with the use of new, already available technologies that reduce the environmental burden and the amount of emission charges,
- Use of the funds collected from the sale of the EU ETS and their increase through government subsidies in order to accelerate the development of RES and "skip" the current gas phase,
- Development of hydrogen technologies in electricity generation and heating and the use of natural gas infrastructure for the acceleration of a hydrogen-based economy,
- Setting new goals and activities in the field of restructuring of the hard coal and lignite mining industry as a consequence of the new energy policy developed (increased efficiency, new technologies, intensification of structural reconstruction), based on the optimization of the energy mix and the context of energy security.

However, it should be noted that these changes may be accelerated due to the Russian invasion in Ukraine. As a result of the European Union's support for the Ukrainian people and of the attempt to reduce

Russian gas purchases, we are seeing old coal-fired power plants being brought online, and the European Commission itself has changed its position on nuclear power. It should also be noted that some current trends such as cryptocurrency mining can mean a large increase in energy consumption (Náñez Alonso et al., 2020, 2021a, 2021b; Náñez Alonso, 2023). In addition, geopolitical tensions in the Middle East may affect the supply of gas and oil, so energy policy in Europe is facing a period of even more uncertainty (Peña-Ramos et al., 2020; Adam and Yacob, 2022).

6. Conclusions

As illustrated, the countries of the European Union are implementing the energy transition at different rates and in different ways. Its pace depends on many factors, including those related to the implementation of a number of global, European, national and local climate commitments. When implementing the climate and energy policy, the European Union bodies consistently exert pressure on Member States to jointly reduce greenhouse gas emissions, increase the share of renewable energy and improve energy efficiency (Dunlop, 2023). The value of the conducted research should be perceived in two basic layers, i.e. theoretical-methodological and utilitarian, empirical. In the theoretical-methodological layer, the added value of the research was the use of the method of taxonomy of structures for the comparative analysis of structures of the energy mix. This approach has made it possible, for the first time, to conduct a fully synthetic and long-term analysis of this issue in the area of the European Union. In turn, the results of the conducted research brought several key findings, determining their added value in the utilitarian layer. The following conclusions should be made in that regard.

- Firstly, studies have shown a clear correlation between the implemented climate and energy policy of the EU and changes in the energy mix of member states - confirmation of the partial hypothesis **H1**.
- Secondly, the research has clearly shown a significant increase in the share of renewable and low-emission sources in the energy mix of the EU countries - confirmation of the partial hypothesis **H2** and **H3**.
- Thirdly, the research has also shown a decreasing degree of concentration of the energy mix, which indicates the growing diversification of energy generation sources in the EU countries, including countries traditionally based on coal (Poland) - confirmation of the partial hypothesis **H3**.
- Fourthly, simultaneously with the ongoing deconcentration of structures, the studies have shown the existence of a process of similarity of the structures (energy mix) of the surveyed countries in relation to the entire EU (EU27/EU25) - confirmation of the partial hypothesis **H3**.

Briefly extending the first of the key findings in the utilitarian layer, it should be added that the correlation between the implementation of the climate and energy policy and changes in the energy mix occurred both in the countries of the so-called old Union (EU15), represented in the research by Spain, and in the countries adopted after 2004, represented in the research by Poland, what confirms the main hypothesis (H). In addition, this correlation has also been identified in the EU treated as a single organism (a research object with an individualised structure). With regard to the occurrence of two proven processes, i.e. the progressive deconcentration of the energy mix and the similarity of its structure, it should be clearly emphasized as a result of the conducted research that the acceleration of these processes was clearly influenced by the adoption of the common climate policy (confirmation of the partial hypothesis **H3**), obliging and not only encouraging Member States, through various pressure mechanisms, to take specific actions. This underlines the importance of a common EU policy in halting an adverse climate (confirmation of the partial hypothesis **H1** and **H3**).

Undoubtedly, the research carried out, like any scientific inference, has certain limitations. The research was carried out with the use of the triangulation system, i.e. three objects with specific structures. These objects were countries representing the EU15 and the ones adopted after 2004 as well as the EU treated as a single object (an organism with a structure derived from heterogeneous elements). The adoption of such a solution undoubtedly narrows the field of exploration, limiting the possibility of wider inference and finding possible deviations from the regularities demonstrated in the research. Nevertheless, this approach has been chosen as these are introductory pilot studies that may be broadened in the future. Proven relationships as key findings in the utilitarian layer and the demonstrated usefulness of research methods are the basis for continuing research in several directions. Firstly, the aim of further research will be to analyse the energy mix of all EU countries (as individual objects) in an analogous, long period (1990–2020). Secondly, there will be a comparison of the tools used in the process of the energy transition in individual countries. Thirdly, a methodology will be developed and countries will be grouped according to the degree of similarity of individual structures. Thanks to such research planning, current and future ones will allow to develop a model of the energy transition in the long term and will contribute to a better understanding of individual elements of the energy transition management system.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Javier Jorge-Vazquez: Formal analysis, Investigation, Supervision, Validation. **Jarosław Kaczmarek:** Investigation, Methodology, Supervision, Validation, Visualization, Conceptualization, Formal analysis. **Lilla Knop:** Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Supervision, Validation, Visualization, Writing – review & editing. **Konrad Kolegowicz:** Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Sergio Luis Náñez Alonso:** Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Investigation, Supervision, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft. **Wojciech Szymła:** Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Investigation, Supervision, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix

Matrix 1. Intensity of changes in the structure of energy mix (NPS) in Poland in 1990–2020

1990	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
0,000	0,018	0,058	0,022	0,041	0,082	0,120	0,131	0,133	0,184	0,172	0,183	0,231	0,232	0,285	0,371	0,401	0,405	0,498	0,525	0,486	0,473	0,458	0,450	0,413	0,426	0,434	0,474	0,454	0,575	0,571
0,018	0,000	0,058	0,025	0,032	0,082	0,104	0,115	0,116	0,184	0,172	0,166	0,230	0,225	0,278	0,364	0,394	0,402	0,498	0,518	0,488	0,474	0,459	0,452	0,414	0,422	0,430	0,474	0,455	0,576	0,572
0,058	0,058	0,000	0,040	0,059	0,042	0,136	0,153	0,139	0,130	0,127	0,188	0,193	0,233	0,254	0,342	0,376	0,399	0,496	0,515	0,504	0,472	0,456	0,461	0,433	0,419	0,441	0,472	0,455	0,574	0,569
0,022	0,025	0,040	0,000	0,033	0,063	0,126	0,136	0,138	0,165	0,153	0,188	0,225	0,233	0,282	0,368	0,398	0,402	0,499	0,522	0,488	0,475	0,459	0,452	0,414	0,423	0,431	0,475	0,456	0,577	0,572
0,041	0,032	0,059	0,033	0,000	0,049	0,092	0,103	0,104	0,151	0,139	0,155	0,208	0,212	0,265	0,351	0,381	0,389	0,485	0,505	0,475	0,462	0,446	0,439	0,401	0,409	0,417	0,461	0,442	0,563	0,559
0,082	0,082	0,042	0,063	0,049	0,000	0,105	0,120	0,109	0,115	0,103	0,160	0,180	0,205	0,239	0,326	0,360	0,383	0,479	0,499	0,473	0,456	0,440	0,433	0,402	0,403	0,411	0,456	0,437	0,557	0,553
0,120	0,104	0,136	0,126	0,092	0,105	0,000	0,091	0,087	0,167	0,156	0,127	0,215	0,182	0,235	0,315	0,343	0,366	0,462	0,481	0,452	0,438	0,423	0,416	0,379	0,386	0,394	0,438	0,420	0,540	0,536
0,131	0,115	0,153	0,136	0,103	0,120	0,091	0,000	0,032	0,087	0,078	0,059	0,133	0,121	0,175	0,260	0,289	0,306	0,402	0,421	0,392	0,378	0,363	0,355	0,318	0,326	0,334	0,378	0,358	0,479	0,475
0,133	0,116	0,139	0,138	0,104	0,109	0,087	0,032	0,000	0,081	0,071	0,055	0,132	0,115	0,172	0,258	0,292	0,315	0,411	0,430	0,401	0,387	0,372	0,364	0,327	0,335	0,343	0,387	0,367	0,488	0,484
0,184	0,184	0,130	0,165	0,151	0,115	0,167	0,087	0,081	0,000	0,029	0,087	0,069	0,144	0,159	0,243	0,278	0,300	0,397	0,416	0,415	0,372	0,357	0,371	0,344	0,320	0,351	0,372	0,365	0,474	0,477
0,172	0,172	0,127	0,153	0,139	0,103	0,156	0,078	0,071	0,029	0,000	0,065	0,080	0,119	0,152	0,238	0,273	0,295	0,391	0,410	0,390	0,367	0,352	0,347	0,319	0,315	0,327	0,367	0,348	0,469	0,465
0,183	0,166	0,188	0,188	0,155	0,160	0,127	0,059	0,055	0,087	0,065	0,000	0,093	0,075	0,135	0,221	0,256	0,279	0,376	0,395	0,365	0,352	0,336	0,329	0,291	0,299	0,307	0,352	0,333	0,454	0,449
0,231	0,230	0,193	0,225	0,208	0,180	0,215	0,133	0,132	0,069	0,080	0,093	0,000	0,090	0,105	0,178	0,212	0,235	0,331	0,349	0,363	0,310	0,290	0,319	0,292	0,258	0,299	0,306	0,313	0,407	0,425
0,232	0,225	0,233	0,233	0,212	0,205	0,182	0,121	0,115	0,144	0,119	0,075	0,090	0,000	0,060	0,151	0,185	0,208	0,304	0,322	0,290	0,277	0,261	0,254	0,217	0,225	0,233	0,277	0,258	0,379	0,374
0,285	0,278	0,254	0,282	0,265	0,239	0,235	0,175	0,172	0,159	0,152	0,135	0,105	0,060	0,000	0,092	0,126	0,149	0,245	0,262	0,258	0,218	0,202	0,215	0,218	0,179	0,202	0,218	0,209	0,320	0,320
0,371	0,364	0,342	0,368	0,351	0,326	0,315	0,260	0,258	0,243	0,238	0,221	0,178	0,151	0,092	0,000	0,057	0,079	0,158	0,193	0,222	0,163	0,151	0,243	0,254	0,201	0,247	0,183	0,232	0,265	0,308
0,401	0,394	0,376	0,398	0,381	0,360	0,343	0,289	0,292	0,278	0,273	0,256	0,212	0,185	0,126	0,057	0,000	0,040	0,119	0,139	0,165	0,119	0,142	0,218	0,228	0,174	0,219	0,176	0,205	0,210	0,281
0,405	0,402	0,399	0,402	0,389	0,383	0,366	0,306	0,315	0,300	0,295	0,279	0,235	0,208	0,149	0,079	0,040	0,000	0,104	0,120	0,162	0,120	0,148	0,221	0,233	0,180	0,226	0,181	0,210	0,212	0,286
0,498	0,498	0,496	0,499	0,485	0,479	0,462	0,402	0,411	0,397	0,391	0,376	0,331	0,304	0,245	0,158	0,119	0,104	0,000	0,062	0,146	0,110	0,149	0,209	0,223	0,198	0,216	0,162	0,198	0,197	0,273
0,525	0,518	0,515	0,522	0,505	0,499	0,481	0,421	0,430	0,416	0,410	0,395	0,349	0,322	0,262	0,193	0,139	0,120	0,062	0,000	0,101	0,090	0,152	0,182	0,212	0,183	0,178	0,165	0,167	0,154	0,228
0,486	0,488	0,504	0,488	0,475	0,473	0,452	0,392	0,401	0,415	0,390	0,365	0,363	0,290	0,258	0,222	0,165	0,162	0,146	0,101	0,000	0,077	0,142	0,134	0,150	0,169	0,128	0,157	0,125	0,106	0,150
0,473	0,474	0,472	0,475	0,462	0,456	0,438	0,378	0,387	0,372	0,367	0,352	0,310	0,277	0,218	0,163	0,119	0,120	0,110	0,090	0,077	0,000	0,080	0,102	0,125	0,107	0,116	0,099	0,093	0,119	0,166
0,458	0,459	0,456	0,459	0,446	0,440	0,423	0,363	0,372	0,357	0,352	0,336	0,290	0,261	0,202	0,151	0,142	0,148	0,149	0,152	0,142	0,080	0,000	0,102	0,107	0,066	0,107	0,040	0,088	0,142	0,176
0,450	0,452	0,461	0,452	0,439	0,433	0,416	0,355	0,364	0,371	0,347	0,329	0,319	0,254	0,215	0,243	0,218	0,221	0,209	0,182	0,134	0,102	0,102	0,000	0,041	0,066	0,034	0,084	0,023	0,140	0,143
0,413	0,414	0,433	0,414	0,401	0,402	0,379	0,318	0,327	0,344	0,319	0,291	0,292	0,217	0,218	0,254	0,228	0,233	0,223	0,212	0,150	0,125	0,107	0,041	0,000	0,056	0,044	0,088	0,047	0,171	0,174
0,426	0,422	0,419	0,423	0,409	0,403	0,386	0,326	0,335	0,320	0,315	0,299	0,258	0,225	0,179	0,201	0,174	0,180	0,198	0,183	0,169	0,107	0,066	0,066	0,056	0,000	0,052	0,059	0,059	0,164	0,185
0,434	0,430	0,441	0,431	0,417	0,411	0,394	0,334	0,343	0,351	0,327	0,307	0,299	0,233	0,202	0,247	0,219	0,226	0,216	0,178	0,128	0,116	0,107	0,034	0,044	0,052	0,000	0,076	0,034	0,147	0,150
0,474	0,474	0,472	0,475	0,461	0,456	0,438	0,378	0,387	0,372	0,367	0,352	0,306	0,277	0,218	0,183	0,176	0,181	0,162	0,165	0,157	0,099	0,040	0,084	0,088	0,059	0,076	0,000	0,067	0,129	0,162
0,454	0,455	0,455	0,456	0,442	0,437	0,420	0,358	0,367	0,365	0,348	0,333	0,313	0,258	0,209	0,232	0,205	0,210	0,198	0,167	0,125	0,093	0,088	0,023	0,047	0,059	0,034	0,067	0,000	0,133	0,135
0,575	0,576	0,574	0,577	0,563	0,557	0,540	0,479	0,488	0,474	0,469	0,454	0,407	0,379	0,320	0,265	0,210	0,212	0,197	0,154	0,106	0,119	0,142	0,140	0,171	0,164	0,147	0,129	0,133	0,000	0,076
0,571	0,572	0,569	0,572	0,559	0,553	0,536	0,475	0,484	0,477	0,465	0,449	0,425	0,374	0,320	0,308	0,281	0,286	0,273	0,228	0,150	0,166	0,176	0,143	0,174	0,185	0,150	0,162	0,135	0,076	0,000

Matrix 2. Intensity of changes in the structure of energy mix (NPS) in Spain in 1990–2020

1990	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
0,000	0,018	0,058	0,022	0,041	0,082	0,120	0,131	0,133	0,184	0,172	0,183	0,231	0,232	0,285	0,371	0,401	0,405	0,498	0,525	0,486	0,473	0,458	0,450	0,413	0,426	0,434	0,474	0,454	0,575	0,571
0,018	0,000	0,058	0,025	0,032	0,082	0,104	0,115	0,116	0,184	0,172	0,166	0,230	0,225	0,278	0,364	0,394	0,402	0,498	0,518	0,488	0,474	0,459	0,452	0,414	0,422	0,430	0,474	0,455	0,576	0,572
0,058	0,058	0,000	0,040	0,059	0,042	0,136	0,153	0,139	0,130	0,127	0,188	0,193	0,233	0,254	0,342	0,376	0,399	0,496	0,515	0,504	0,472	0,456	0,461	0,433	0,419	0,441	0,472	0,455	0,574	0,569
0,022	0,025	0,040	0,000	0,033	0,063	0,126	0,136	0,138	0,165	0,153	0,188	0,225	0,233	0,282	0,368	0,398	0,402	0,499	0,522	0,488	0,475	0,459	0,452	0,414	0,423	0,431	0,475	0,456	0,577	0,572
0,041	0,032	0,059	0,033	0,000	0,049	0,092	0,103	0,104	0,151	0,139	0,155	0,208	0,212	0,265	0,351	0,381	0,389	0,485	0,505	0,475	0,462	0,446	0,439	0,401	0,409	0,417	0,461	0,442	0,563	0,559
0,082	0,082	0,042	0,063	0,049	0,000	0,105	0,120	0,109	0,115	0,103	0,160	0,180																		

(continued)

Matrix 2. Intensity of changes in the structure of energy mix (NPS) in Spain in 1990–2020

1990	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
0,486	0,488	0,504	0,488	0,475	0,473	0,452	0,392	0,401	0,415	0,390	0,365	0,363	0,290	0,258	0,222	0,165	0,162	0,146	0,101	0,000	0,077	0,142	0,134	0,150	0,169	0,128	0,157	0,125	0,106	0,150
0,473	0,474	0,472	0,475	0,462	0,456	0,438	0,378	0,387	0,372	0,367	0,352	0,310	0,277	0,218	0,163	0,119	0,120	0,110	0,090	0,077	0,000	0,080	0,102	0,125	0,107	0,116	0,099	0,093	0,119	0,166
0,458	0,459	0,456	0,459	0,446	0,440	0,423	0,363	0,372	0,357	0,352	0,336	0,290	0,261	0,202	0,151	0,142	0,148	0,149	0,152	0,142	0,080	0,000	0,102	0,107	0,066	0,107	0,040	0,088	0,142	0,176
0,450	0,452	0,461	0,452	0,439	0,433	0,416	0,355	0,364	0,371	0,347	0,329	0,319	0,254	0,215	0,243	0,218	0,221	0,209	0,182	0,134	0,102	0,102	0,000	0,041	0,066	0,034	0,084	0,023	0,140	0,143
0,413	0,414	0,433	0,414	0,401	0,402	0,379	0,318	0,327	0,344	0,319	0,291	0,292	0,217	0,218	0,254	0,228	0,233	0,223	0,212	0,150	0,125	0,107	0,041	0,000	0,056	0,044	0,088	0,047	0,171	0,174
0,426	0,422	0,419	0,423	0,409	0,403	0,386	0,326	0,335	0,320	0,315	0,299	0,258	0,225	0,179	0,201	0,174	0,180	0,198	0,183	0,169	0,107	0,066	0,066	0,056	0,000	0,052	0,059	0,059	0,164	0,185
0,434	0,430	0,441	0,431	0,417	0,411	0,394	0,334	0,343	0,351	0,327	0,307	0,299	0,233	0,202	0,247	0,219	0,226	0,216	0,178	0,128	0,116	0,107	0,034	0,044	0,052	0,000	0,076	0,034	0,147	0,150
0,474	0,474	0,472	0,475	0,461	0,456	0,438	0,378	0,387	0,372	0,367	0,352	0,306	0,277	0,218	0,183	0,176	0,181	0,162	0,165	0,157	0,099	0,040	0,084	0,088	0,059	0,076	0,000	0,067	0,129	0,162
0,454	0,455	0,455	0,456	0,442	0,437	0,420	0,358	0,367	0,365	0,348	0,333	0,313	0,258	0,209	0,232	0,205	0,210	0,198	0,167	0,125	0,093	0,088	0,023	0,047	0,059	0,034	0,067	0,000	0,133	0,135
0,575	0,576	0,574	0,577	0,563	0,557	0,540	0,479	0,488	0,474	0,469	0,454	0,407	0,379	0,320	0,265	0,210	0,212	0,197	0,154	0,106	0,119	0,142	0,140	0,171	0,164	0,147	0,129	0,133	0,000	0,076
0,571	0,572	0,569	0,572	0,559	0,553	0,536	0,475	0,484	0,477	0,465	0,449	0,425	0,374	0,320	0,308	0,281	0,286	0,273	0,228	0,150	0,166	0,176	0,143	0,174	0,185	0,150	0,162	0,135	0,076	0,000

Matrix 3. Intensity of changes in the structure of energy mix (NPS) in EU27 (including Poland and Spain) in 1990–2020

1990	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
0,000	0,014	0,026	0,033	0,029	0,032	0,036	0,049	0,052	0,067	0,071	0,085	0,083	0,092	0,110	0,134	0,147	0,168	0,189	0,197	0,207	0,219	0,214	0,210	0,210	0,230	0,254	0,289	0,285	0,338	0,374
0,014	0,000	0,017	0,026	0,023	0,024	0,032	0,045	0,048	0,064	0,068	0,081	0,083	0,095	0,113	0,138	0,150	0,171	0,192	0,200	0,208	0,222	0,217	0,210	0,209	0,233	0,257	0,292	0,288	0,341	0,375
0,026	0,017	0,000	0,016	0,017	0,017	0,028	0,041	0,042	0,058	0,064	0,075	0,083	0,098	0,116	0,141	0,153	0,174	0,195	0,203	0,211	0,225	0,220	0,213	0,209	0,236	0,260	0,295	0,291	0,344	0,378
0,033	0,026	0,016	0,000	0,010	0,017	0,022	0,029	0,039	0,053	0,061	0,070	0,078	0,095	0,112	0,138	0,150	0,171	0,192	0,199	0,208	0,221	0,216	0,209	0,205	0,233	0,256	0,291	0,287	0,340	0,374
0,029	0,023	0,017	0,010	0,000	0,009	0,017	0,030	0,034	0,049	0,056	0,064	0,073	0,090	0,108	0,133	0,145	0,166	0,187	0,194	0,203	0,217	0,211	0,204	0,200	0,228	0,252	0,286	0,282	0,335	0,369
0,032	0,024	0,017	0,017	0,009	0,000	0,013	0,026	0,030	0,045	0,052	0,063	0,070	0,086	0,104	0,129	0,141	0,163	0,183	0,190	0,199	0,213	0,207	0,200	0,197	0,224	0,248	0,283	0,278	0,331	0,365
0,036	0,032	0,028	0,022	0,017	0,013	0,000	0,015	0,026	0,039	0,047	0,059	0,062	0,079	0,097	0,121	0,134	0,155	0,176	0,182	0,192	0,206	0,200	0,193	0,189	0,217	0,240	0,275	0,271	0,323	0,357
0,049	0,045	0,041	0,029	0,030	0,026	0,015	0,000	0,015	0,026	0,034	0,046	0,050	0,067	0,085	0,109	0,122	0,143	0,164	0,172	0,180	0,194	0,188	0,182	0,177	0,205	0,229	0,263	0,259	0,312	0,347
0,052	0,048	0,042	0,039	0,034	0,030	0,026	0,015	0,000	0,018	0,026	0,035	0,045	0,057	0,075	0,099	0,112	0,133	0,153	0,161	0,170	0,184	0,178	0,172	0,168	0,195	0,219	0,254	0,249	0,302	0,336
0,067	0,064	0,058	0,053	0,049	0,045	0,039	0,026	0,018	0,000	0,016	0,025	0,031	0,049	0,060	0,084	0,097	0,118	0,139	0,147	0,155	0,169	0,164	0,157	0,153	0,180	0,204	0,239	0,235	0,287	0,322
0,071	0,068	0,064	0,061	0,056	0,052	0,047	0,034	0,026	0,016	0,000	0,014	0,023	0,039	0,053	0,077	0,090	0,111	0,131	0,139	0,148	0,162	0,156	0,150	0,146	0,172	0,197	0,232	0,227	0,280	0,314
0,085	0,081	0,075	0,070	0,064	0,063	0,059	0,046	0,035	0,025	0,014	0,000	0,023	0,041	0,051	0,071	0,083	0,104	0,124	0,132	0,141	0,154	0,149	0,142	0,143	0,165	0,189	0,224	0,220	0,272	0,307
0,083	0,083	0,083	0,078	0,073	0,070	0,062	0,050	0,045	0,031	0,023	0,023	0,000	0,027	0,036	0,061	0,073	0,094	0,114	0,122	0,139	0,144	0,139	0,143	0,152	0,154	0,181	0,214	0,210	0,262	0,305
0,092	0,095	0,098	0,095	0,090	0,086	0,079	0,067	0,057	0,049	0,039	0,041	0,027	0,000	0,022	0,043	0,056	0,077	0,097	0,113	0,130	0,127	0,126	0,139	0,156	0,157	0,171	0,197	0,200	0,246	0,296
0,110	0,113	0,116	0,112	0,108	0,104	0,097	0,085	0,075	0,060	0,053	0,051	0,036	0,022	0,000	0,025	0,038	0,059	0,079	0,091	0,108	0,109	0,104	0,127	0,144	0,145	0,149	0,179	0,178	0,228	0,274
0,134	0,138	0,141	0,138	0,133	0,129	0,121	0,109	0,099	0,084	0,077	0,071	0,061	0,043	0,025	0,000	0,015	0,037	0,056	0,072	0,089	0,085	0,097	0,126	0,143	0,144	0,147	0,155	0,169	0,205	0,255
0,147	0,150	0,153	0,150	0,145	0,141	0,134	0,122	0,112	0,097	0,090	0,083	0,073	0,056	0,038	0,015	0,000	0,025	0,045	0,060	0,078	0,072	0,092	0,121	0,138	0,139	0,142	0,147	0,164	0,194	0,244
0,168	0,171	0,174	0,171	0,166	0,163	0,155	0,143	0,133	0,118	0,111	0,104	0,094	0,077	0,059	0,037	0,025	0,000	0,029	0,042	0,059	0,053	0,082	0,111	0,128	0,130	0,133	0,136	0,155	0,175	0,225
0,189	0,192	0,195	0,192	0,187	0,183	0,176	0,164	0,153	0,139	0,131	0,124	0,114	0,097	0,079	0,056	0,045	0,029	0,000	0,022	0,040	0,047	0,072	0,098	0,115	0,116	0,119	0,127	0,141	0,158	0,203
0,197	0,200	0,203	0,199	0,194	0,190	0,182	0,172	0,161	0,147	0,139	0,132	0,122	0,113	0,091	0,072	0,060	0,042	0,022	0,000	0,022	0,036	0,059	0,083	0,097	0,098	0,101	0,116	0,123	0,145	0,185
0,207	0,208	0,211	0,208	0,203	0,199	0,192	0,180	0,170	0,155	0,148	0,141	0,139	0,130	0,108	0,089	0,078	0,059	0,040	0,022	0,000	0,033	0,059	0,072	0,081	0,093	0,087	0,104	0,110	0,134	0,167
0,219	0,222	0,225	0,221	0,217	0,213	0,206	0,194	0,184	0,169	0,162	0,154	0,144	0,127	0,109	0,085	0,072	0,053	0,047	0,036	0,033	0,000	0,035	0,064	0,075	0,078	0,080	0,082	0,102	0,125	0,175
0,214	0,217	0,220	0,216	0,211	0,207	0,200	0,188	0,178	0,164	0,156	0,149	0,139	0,126	0,104	0,097	0,092	0,082	0,072	0,059	0,059	0,035	0,000	0,031	0,054	0,048	0,051	0,075	0,074	0,124	0,170
0,210	0,210	0,213	0,209	0,204	0,200	0,193	0,182	0,172	0,157	0,150	0,142	0,143	0,139	0,127	0,126	0,121	0,111	0,098	0,083	0,072	0,064	0,031	0,000	0,025	0,030	0,048	0,083	0,078	0,131	0,165
0,210	0,209	0,209	0,205	0,200	0,197	0,189	0,177	0,168	0,153	0,146	0,143	0,152	0,156	0,144	0,143	0,138	0,128	0,115	0,097	0,081	0,075	0,054	0,025	0,000	0,031	0,051	0,086	0,082	0,135	0,169
0,230	0,233	0,236	0,233	0,228	0,224	0,217	0,205	0,195	0,180	0,172	0,165	0,154	0,157	0,145																

(continued)

Matrix 4. Intensity of changes in the structure of energy mix (NPS) in EU25 (excluding Poland and Spain) in 1990–2020

1990	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
0,035	0,029	0,019	0,014	0,006	0,000	0,019	0,027	0,029	0,047	0,052	0,060	0,070	0,082	0,096	0,114	0,125	0,146	0,157	0,162	0,177	0,195	0,188	0,182	0,180	0,210	0,237	0,273	0,269	0,314	0,352
0,034	0,032	0,033	0,025	0,023	0,019	0,000	0,018	0,028	0,048	0,056	0,062	0,060	0,075	0,088	0,107	0,118	0,139	0,150	0,155	0,170	0,188	0,181	0,177	0,178	0,203	0,230	0,265	0,262	0,307	0,347
0,050	0,048	0,044	0,029	0,031	0,027	0,018	0,000	0,019	0,035	0,043	0,049	0,052	0,067	0,080	0,098	0,108	0,130	0,141	0,148	0,161	0,179	0,172	0,166	0,166	0,194	0,222	0,257	0,254	0,299	0,337
0,053	0,051	0,044	0,037	0,032	0,029	0,028	0,019	0,000	0,024	0,033	0,042	0,051	0,060	0,069	0,086	0,096	0,118	0,129	0,135	0,149	0,167	0,160	0,154	0,152	0,182	0,209	0,245	0,241	0,287	0,325
0,077	0,075	0,064	0,052	0,051	0,047	0,048	0,035	0,024	0,000	0,017	0,023	0,033	0,055	0,055	0,070	0,081	0,104	0,113	0,120	0,134	0,151	0,144	0,139	0,142	0,166	0,194	0,229	0,226	0,271	0,309
0,080	0,078	0,068	0,060	0,056	0,052	0,056	0,043	0,033	0,017	0,000	0,010	0,021	0,041	0,046	0,062	0,073	0,095	0,105	0,111	0,126	0,143	0,136	0,131	0,138	0,158	0,186	0,221	0,218	0,263	0,301
0,089	0,087	0,077	0,067	0,064	0,060	0,062	0,049	0,042	0,023	0,010	0,000	0,018	0,039	0,044	0,057	0,068	0,089	0,099	0,105	0,119	0,136	0,130	0,124	0,136	0,154	0,179	0,215	0,211	0,256	0,295
0,086	0,087	0,088	0,074	0,074	0,070	0,060	0,052	0,051	0,033	0,021	0,018	0,000	0,031	0,035	0,050	0,060	0,082	0,092	0,100	0,119	0,130	0,124	0,127	0,145	0,151	0,172	0,208	0,204	0,249	0,297
0,096	0,098	0,098	0,090	0,086	0,082	0,075	0,067	0,060	0,055	0,041	0,039	0,031	0,000	0,024	0,040	0,047	0,067	0,085	0,099	0,116	0,114	0,122	0,138	0,156	0,162	0,170	0,191	0,202	0,243	0,296
0,111	0,112	0,113	0,104	0,099	0,096	0,088	0,080	0,069	0,055	0,046	0,044	0,035	0,024	0,000	0,018	0,029	0,051	0,062	0,076	0,093	0,099	0,099	0,121	0,139	0,146	0,147	0,177	0,179	0,220	0,273
0,127	0,128	0,128	0,122	0,118	0,114	0,107	0,098	0,086	0,070	0,062	0,057	0,050	0,040	0,018	0,000	0,017	0,039	0,045	0,059	0,077	0,081	0,093	0,116	0,134	0,141	0,141	0,160	0,168	0,203	0,256
0,131	0,133	0,137	0,133	0,129	0,125	0,118	0,108	0,096	0,081	0,073	0,068	0,060	0,047	0,029	0,017	0,000	0,027	0,039	0,053	0,069	0,073	0,093	0,113	0,131	0,137	0,138	0,149	0,165	0,195	0,249
0,150	0,154	0,157	0,154	0,150	0,146	0,139	0,130	0,118	0,104	0,095	0,089	0,082	0,067	0,051	0,039	0,027	0,000	0,022	0,034	0,051	0,049	0,081	0,104	0,122	0,129	0,129	0,137	0,156	0,177	0,231
0,162	0,166	0,169	0,165	0,161	0,157	0,150	0,141	0,129	0,113	0,105	0,099	0,092	0,085	0,062	0,045	0,039	0,022	0,000	0,019	0,031	0,045	0,069	0,091	0,108	0,115	0,115	0,130	0,141	0,161	0,211
0,169	0,173	0,176	0,171	0,167	0,162	0,155	0,148	0,135	0,120	0,111	0,105	0,100	0,099	0,076	0,059	0,053	0,034	0,019	0,000	0,021	0,037	0,055	0,080	0,093	0,101	0,102	0,122	0,129	0,153	0,198
0,185	0,186	0,189	0,185	0,181	0,177	0,170	0,161	0,149	0,134	0,126	0,119	0,119	0,116	0,093	0,077	0,069	0,051	0,031	0,021	0,000	0,032	0,051	0,068	0,080	0,090	0,091	0,110	0,119	0,142	0,180
0,199	0,203	0,207	0,203	0,198	0,195	0,188	0,179	0,167	0,151	0,143	0,136	0,130	0,114	0,099	0,081	0,073	0,049	0,045	0,037	0,032	0,000	0,038	0,066	0,075	0,083	0,081	0,087	0,108	0,129	0,183
0,193	0,197	0,200	0,196	0,192	0,188	0,181	0,172	0,160	0,144	0,136	0,130	0,124	0,122	0,099	0,093	0,093	0,081	0,069	0,055	0,051	0,038	0,000	0,031	0,050	0,048	0,050	0,085	0,082	0,127	0,174
0,193	0,194	0,194	0,190	0,185	0,182	0,177	0,166	0,154	0,139	0,131	0,124	0,127	0,138	0,121	0,116	0,113	0,104	0,091	0,080	0,068	0,066	0,031	0,000	0,027	0,034	0,056	0,091	0,088	0,134	0,172
0,194	0,195	0,192	0,188	0,183	0,180	0,178	0,166	0,152	0,142	0,138	0,136	0,145	0,156	0,139	0,134	0,131	0,122	0,108	0,093	0,080	0,075	0,050	0,027	0,000	0,031	0,058	0,093	0,090	0,135	0,174
0,216	0,219	0,223	0,218	0,214	0,210	0,203	0,194	0,182	0,166	0,158	0,154	0,151	0,162	0,146	0,141	0,137	0,129	0,115	0,101	0,090	0,083	0,048	0,034	0,031	0,000	0,028	0,064	0,060	0,105	0,152
0,243	0,247	0,250	0,245	0,241	0,237	0,230	0,222	0,209	0,194	0,186	0,179	0,172	0,170	0,147	0,141	0,138	0,129	0,115	0,102	0,091	0,081	0,050	0,056	0,058	0,028	0,000	0,036	0,033	0,079	0,126
0,278	0,282	0,285	0,281	0,276	0,273	0,265	0,257	0,245	0,229	0,221	0,215	0,208	0,191	0,177	0,160	0,149	0,137	0,130	0,122	0,110	0,087	0,085	0,091	0,093	0,064	0,036	0,000	0,026	0,059	0,105
0,275	0,279	0,282	0,278	0,273	0,269	0,262	0,254	0,241	0,226	0,218	0,211	0,204	0,202	0,179	0,168	0,165	0,156	0,141	0,129	0,119	0,108	0,082	0,088	0,090	0,060	0,033	0,026	0,000	0,049	0,094
0,321	0,324	0,328	0,323	0,318	0,314	0,307	0,299	0,287	0,271	0,263	0,256	0,249	0,243	0,220	0,203	0,195	0,177	0,161	0,153	0,142	0,129	0,127	0,134	0,135	0,105	0,079	0,059	0,049	0,000	0,053
0,365	0,365	0,366	0,361	0,356	0,352	0,347	0,337	0,325	0,309	0,301	0,295	0,297	0,296	0,273	0,256	0,249	0,231	0,211	0,198	0,180	0,183	0,174	0,172	0,174	0,152	0,126	0,105	0,094	0,053	0,000

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